

those tested earlier. The trial was laid out with rice variety IR8 and 9 levels of potash: 0, 25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150, 175, and 200 kg K/ha. Potash was applied basally at the time of planting and no insecticide was used. Whorl maggot infestation was assessed 30 days after

transplanting on the basis of percentage of damaged tillers.

The results revealed that whorl maggot damage increased only at the two highest rates of potash (see table). Plants with 175 or 200 kg K/ha had significantly higher whorl maggot dam-

age than those with 0-75 kg K/ha. But the grain yield differences were not statistically significant.

The local fertilizer recommendation is only 50 kg K/ha. Potash application at that level is not expected to increase whorl maggot damage in rice. ■

Control of daphnids in blue-green algae multiplication plots

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The main problem in field multiplication plots is the damage caused by daphnids that live on the soil surface and form small mud tunnels. Usually, daphnids lie horizontally on the soil surface. When conditions are favorable, the population buildup is so heavy that space becomes unavailable. The daphnids then stick one end of their nests in the soil substrate in a standing water column. If the blue-green algae (BGA) multiplication site is left unprotected, the dense mass of BGA growing on the water surface will vanish within a couple of days because of the severity of damage caused by daphnids.

To develop a suitable control measure, three randomized replicated trials during 1979 kuruvai tested seven granular insecticides in three concentrations (normal, double, triple doses). Because BGA already were established in the field, no BGA seed material was applied to the experimental plots. P₂O₅ in the form of superphosphate was applied uniformly to supply 32 kg/ha to all plots as a nutrient for algal activity. The granular insecticides were applied as per treatment. Water depth was maintained permanently at 10 cm. On the 10th day, the BGA mass floating on the water surface was collected separately for each treatment. It was spread on a threshing floor and allowed to dry in the sun. The dried algal flakes were collected and weighed.

The results indicated that carbofuran at double dose, and quinalphos, mephosfolan and diazinon at normal doses can be used to control daphnids in BGA multiplication units. ■

Effect of granular insecticides on BGA seed material in multiplication plots. Aduthurai, India.

Insecticide and formulation	Normal rate (kg a.i./ha)	BGA seed material (kg/10 m ²)		
		Normal dose	Double dose	Triple dose
Carbofuran 3% G	0.6	6.1	9.0	8.9
Carbaryl 4% G	0.8	5.0	7.3	5.8
B.H.C. 6.5% G	1.3	3.5	5.7	6.7
Quinalphos 5% G	0.6	8.8	9.1	9.0
Mephosfolan 5% G	0.5	8.6	9.1	7.3
Phorate 10% G	1.3	5.0	6.7	8.0
Diazinon 10% G	1.0	8.5	8.9	9.0
Control		0.8	0.9	0.6
C.D. (P= 0.05%)		1.2	1.6	1.1

Insecticides sprayed on brown planthopper eggs

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Timing insecticide applications for brown planthopper (BPH) control is difficult because at any one time a field population will be composed of eggs, nymphs, and adults. To reduce insecticide cost an insecticide that has efficacy against all stages is desirable. We tested for ovicidal activity insecticides that showed activity against BPH adults. We report on the ovicidal activity of several coded and commercial insecticides.

Two gravid female BPH in each cage oviposited for 24 hours on 30-day-old TN1 plants. After oviposition, the females were removed and the potted plants sprayed with 6.25 ml of insecticidal solution per pot. Hatched nymphs were counted daily and removed until hatching terminated. Unhatched eggs were counted after the plants were dissected.

Among the 12 insecticides used, 6 had high ovicidal activity: UC 54229, FMC 35001, UC SF-1, UC 27867, carbaryl, and azinphos-ethyl (see table). Propoxur, decamethrin, and NNI-750 had low activity. Diazinon, BHC, and chlorpyrifos had no effect. UC 54229, UC SF-1, and UC 27867 are coded car-

Ovicidal activity of foliar sprayed insecticides on *N. lugens* eggs. IRRI greenhouse, 1980.

Common name	Insecticides ^a		Hatched eggs (%) ^b
	Trade name	Formulation	
UC 54229		100% Tech.	0.7 a
FMC 35001	Marshall	20% EC	1.1 a
UC SF-1		40% F	2.7 a
UC 27867		50% WP	2.9 a
Carbaryl	Sevin	85% WP	2.8 a
Azinphos-ethyl	Gusathion A	40% EC	3.9 a
Propoxur	Unden	20% EC	77.6 b
Decamethrin	Decis	2.5% EC	78.1 b
NNI-750		25% WP	80.4 b
Diazinon	Basudin	20% EC	94.0 c
BHC	Lindane	26% WP	96.6 c
Chlorpyrifos	Lorsban	40% EC	96.0 c
Control			97.5 c

^aSprayed at the rate of 0.075% concentration (0.75 kg a.i./ha at a spray volume of 1,000 liters/ha). EC= emulsifiable concentrate, WP = wettable powder, Tech. = technical formulation. ^bAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.